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THE RELATION BETWEEN AUTONOMY AND WELL-BEING IN HIGHER EDUCATION STUDENTS DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

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ABSTRACT

During the COVID-19 pandemic, higher education has drastically moved online, which has increased the importance of autonomous learning by students. A decrease in students' well-being has meanwhile been registered across the globe. In this study, we examine which learning characteristics increase student well-being under the pandemic constraints. We investigate students' well-being, specifically burnout, amotivation, and study engagement, and their relation to learning autonomy. Two types of autonomy were included: autonomy at the student-level and autonomy at the instructor-level, measured via the instructors' communication and support provided for online learning. Our analyses show that amotivation and burnout correlated negatively with both kinds of autonomy. Similarly, student engagement correlated positively with both kinds of autonomy. A multiple regression showed that student-level autonomy was the only variable to significantly predict all three well-being variables, while instructor support predicted only study engagement and burnout. Instructor communication did not predict any well-being variables. Implications, limitations, and future directions for the role of autonomy in online learning are discussed.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Well-being and mental health levels have decreased significantly during the current COVID-19 pandemic. This decrease has been confirmed across the globe, including samples from Hong Kong, United Kingdom, Spain, United States, Denmark^[1], and Bangladesh^[2]. The pandemic has also forced higher educational institutions to move online at short notice. A study^[3] found that most faculties and administrators have started transitioning towards online teaching methods, even if they did not have any previous experience with them. Social distancing policies have led to less face-to-face, direct support from the educational staff.

For online learning to take place, students need to become autonomous/independent learners^[4]. Autonomy is also one of the main tenets of self-determination theory, which asserts that basic psychological needs must be met for higher motivation, self-development, and well-being to be achieved^{[5][6][7]}. Two other important factors are relatedness and competence^{[5][6][7]}. When the need for autonomy is met, students become more motivated and more likely to demonstrate higher study engagement, which leads to higher performance^{[6][8][9]}. High levels of autonomy also have a positive effect on well-being factors such as lower levels of burnout^[10]. Autonomy is usually measured at the student-level, describing how students perceive their autonomy when studying. However, autonomy is a dynamic, socially defined construct^{[5][11]}. This implies that to get a better understanding of its effects, we also need to look at how students interact with their instructor and environment.

In this study, we explore how students' self-reported autonomy had an impact on their motivation and well-being, measured via amotivation, study engagement, and burnout, during the COVID-19 pandemic. We also consider how students' instructors supported and communicated with students to facilitate their autonomy when studying. Such interaction between the students and instructors has been confirmed to have a positive impact on their autonomy^{[9][11][12]}. Thus, we made a clear distinction between self-reported student-level autonomy, and instructor-level autonomy, conceptualized as instructor support and communication. Our research question is: What is the relation between student-level and instructor-level autonomy, and well-being during the COVID-19 pandemic? We hypothesized that student-level autonomy and instructor-level autonomy had a positive relation with each other and with study engagement. Student-level, instructor-level autonomy, and study engagement had a negative relation to amotivation and burnout. We also expected that student-level autonomy and instructor-level autonomy positively predicted study engagement, and negatively predicted amotivation and burnout.

2 METHODOLOGY

1.1 PARTICIPANTS

Participants were recruited using a random sampling method and included all students of one faculty (three bachelor's and four master's programs) at Eindhoven University of Technology. Data were collected through a self-reported questionnaire, at two different points in time: between November and February 2021 for the 1st and 2nd quartile of the 2020-2021 academic year. A total sample of $N = 2404$ was recorded, with a final sample of $N = 1231$, after removing incomplete observations ($N_{Q1} = 617$, $N_{Q2} = 616$). The data collection was approved by the ethical committee of the university.

2.2 MEASURES

The survey consisted of a wide variety of questions related to students' well-being as well as course-specific perceptions. Below, only the questionnaires analyzed in the current study are discussed. The well-being of the students was conceptualized through amotivation, measured via 4 items (ex. "I really felt that I was wasting my time at university") with a Cronbach's $\alpha = .90$, burnout via 8 items (ex. "While I was studying, I often felt emotionally drained") with $\alpha = .87$, and study engagement via 4 items (ex. "I was immersed in my studies") with $\alpha = .90$. Autonomy was measured at the student-level via 5 items (ex. "I could decide on my own what to work on during the course weeks") with $\alpha = .68$, and at instructor-level through instructor communication, 3 items (ex. "Overall, the instructor for this course helped to keep students engaged and participating in productive dialog") with $\alpha = .85$, and through instructor support, 3 items (ex. "The teacher actively facilitated my understanding of the learning materials") with $\alpha = .71$. All items were measured on 1-7 Likert scales.

2.3 STATISTICAL ANALYSES

Descriptive analyses were used to obtain characteristics of the sample. Bivariate correlations were used to assess relations between student-level autonomy, instructor support, instructor communication, amotivation, burnout, and study engagement. We used three multiple regression analyses to predict amotivation, burnout, and study engagement, respectively. For each, the predictors were student-level autonomy, instructor support, and instructor communication. The estimates of the strengths of associations were demonstrated by the standardized β coefficient with a 95% confidence interval (CI). A p-value of $\leq .05$ was considered significant.

3 RESULTS

3.1 DESCRIPTIVE VALUES

Table 1 shows the descriptive values of all variables. These values show that the means change across quartiles, but only slightly. Burnout and amotivation increased between Q1 and Q2 of the 2020-2021 academic year, while study engagement decreased. We found all three autonomy measurements decreased from Q1 to Q2 of the 2020-2021 academic year. We will follow-up on these findings with correlation analyses.

Table 1. Means and Standard Deviations of All Study Variables Across Four Quartiles

Variable	Q1 2020-2021 (n=617)			Q2 2020-2021 (n=616)		
	n	M	SD	n	M	SD
Student Autonomy	617	4.91	0.84	616	4.84	0.90
Instructor Support	616	4.63	1.17	615	4.26	1.18
Instructor Communication	616	4.71	1.29	616	4.51	1.31
Burnout	617	4.16	1.05	493	4.51	1.13
Study engagement	617	3.98	1.01	493	3.68	1.11
Amotivation	617	2.31	1.29	493	2.55	1.49

3.2 CORRELATIONS

Table 2 shows the correlations between the measured variables. Almost all correlations were significant, which is no surprise given the large sample size. The well-being variables correlated as expected: study engagement negatively with burnout ($r(1107) = -.53, p < .001$) and amotivation ($r(1107) = -.41, p < .001$), while burnout and amotivation correlated positively with each other ($r(1107) = .39, p < .001$). According to Cohen's rule of thumbs, these three correlations can be considered medium to high. Study engagement correlated positively with student autonomy ($r(1107) = .34, p < .001$) and both instructor communication ($r(1106) = .15, p < .001$) and support ($r(1106) = .19, p < .001$). As we can see, study engagement has a medium relation with student-level autonomy, but small to medium with instructor-level autonomy. Amotivation had a medium to high negative correlation with student-level autonomy ($r(1107) = -.34, p < .001$) but small negative correlation with instructor support ($r(1106) = -.09, p = .003$) and a non-significant correlation with instructor communication ($r(1106) = -.06, p = .053$). Burnout had a medium to large negative

correlation with student-level autonomy ($r(1107) = -.38, p < .001$) and small to medium negative correlation with instructor support ($r(1106) = -.15, p < .001$) and with instructor communication ($r(1106) = -.09, p = .004$). Student-level autonomy had small to medium positive correlations with instructor support ($r(1229) = .19, p < .001$) and instructor communication ($r(1229) = .13, p < .001$). Instructor support and instructor communication positively correlated with each other ($r(1230) = .64, p < .001$). These correlations show that student-level autonomy had medium to large effect sizes with all three well-being variables, while instructor support and instructor communication only small to medium effect sizes. We found a non-significant relation between instructor communication and amotivation. Student-level autonomy also had small to medium effect sizes with instructor support and instructor communication.

Table 2. Pairwise Correlations Between the Variables, and Sample Sizes

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. Study engagement						
2. Amotivation	-.41*** 1108					
3. Burnout	-.53*** 1108	.39*** 1108				
4. Student Autonomy	.34*** 1108	-.34*** 1108	-.38*** 1108			
5. Instructor support	.19*** 1107	-.09*** 1107	-.15*** 1107	.19*** 1230		
6. Instructor communication	.15*** 1107	-.06 1107	-.09** 1107	.13*** 1230	.64*** 1230	

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

3.3 MULTIPLE REGRESSION ANALYSES

First, a multiple regression analysis was calculated to predict study engagement based on student-level autonomy, instructor support, and instructor communication. The regression was significant ($F(3, 1105) = 58.87, p < .001$) with an adjusted $R^2 = .14$. Student-level autonomy ($\beta = .32, t = 11.28, p < .001$) and instructor support ($\beta = .09, t = 2.56, p = .011$) had significant effects. Student-level autonomy and instructor support significantly predicted study engagement, explaining 14% of the variability. Student-level autonomy had the highest effect size of the two significant

relations. A second multiple regression analysis was calculated to predict amotivation based on the three autonomy variables. The regression was significant ($F(3, 1105) = 49.86, p < .001$) with an adjusted $R^2 = .12$. Student autonomy ($\beta = -.34, t = -11.81, p < .001$) was the only significant predictor. The model explained 12% of the variability with only one significant predictor. Finally, a multiple regression analysis was calculated to predict burnout based on the three autonomy variables. The regression was significant ($F(3, 1105) = 65.67, p < .001$) with an adjusted $R^2 = .15$. Student autonomy ($\beta = -.36, t = -12.89, p < .001$) and instructor support ($\beta = -.09, t = -2.56, p = .012$) had significant effects. The model explained 15% of the variability, the highest amount of the three variables we predicted, with two significant predictors. The results partially confirmed our hypotheses, as student autonomy significantly predicted all three well-being variables, while instructor communication did not predict any. Instructor support significantly predicted study engagement and burnout. The explained variance ranged between 12% for amotivation to 15% for burnout.

4.1 DISCUSSION

Our study took place during the COVID-19 pandemic, a difficult time that changed how higher education approached learning. Our aim was to study the relation between the learning autonomy of higher education students with their mental well-being. We found autonomy, both at the student and the instructor-level, to have negative relations with burnout and amotivation, and positive relations with study engagement. Our findings support our hypotheses, showing that autonomy, both at the student and at the instructor-level, is important to consider when looking at students' well-being. Autonomy is essential in becoming intrinsically motivated. Such motivation contributes to a student becoming actively involved in learning and internalizing their goals^[7]. Study engagement and higher well-being in general are direct consequences when the need for autonomy is met. Our findings fall in line with previous findings, as we found that autonomy at the student-level was the strongest predictor of study engagement, burnout, and amotivation in our study. Student-level autonomy was the only variable to significantly predict amotivation, burnout, as well as study engagement. This shows that autonomy, as perceived by the student, is the most important facet when looking at general learning autonomy. This has various implications when approaching autonomous studying online as a whole. It can be that the environment and instructor lead to the perfect autonomous learning, but students can still feel controlled and underperform. This implies that autonomy targeted practices need to put the students and their beliefs at the forefront.

Online courses give teachers the role of facilitators more than anything. This means that their communication is essential as they can directly encourage students, or indirectly by acknowledging students' accomplishments. The feedback provided by instructors can also play a role in supporting students in their learning. We found that instructors' support did play a direct role when predicting study engagement and burnout of their students. This refers especially to the techniques that instructors

applied during courses, such as appropriate feedback and useful Q&A sessions. Each course has different demands, but also provides different resources for students to efficiently meet those demands. Resources can be directly relevant to the courses' demands, such as feedback and Q&A sessions, but there are also indirect resources, such as general non-directed communication between students and the course instructor. Our findings show that providing directly course relevant resources has a higher impact on well-being than providing indirect resources. Since both measurements looked at how the instructor interacted with the students, we can see that the type of contact and its perceived effectiveness played a higher role in well-being than general communication. Students respond more positively to approaches which target course relevant questions and want their communication with the instructor to be meaningful and helpful. However, both forms of interactions between instructors and students are strongly interconnected; these variables had the highest correlation in our study. It is expected that they share a high amount of variance, and we advise that future studies consider them together. Resources such as support and communication provided by the instructors is easier to address and can be changed more easily compared to self-reported student autonomy, providing a good target for future policies.

These variables represent only two of possible ways in which instructors can enhance students' autonomy and performance. Instructors' feedback and lectures are important in the online environment, but the way in which instructors react and communicate with their students is more important. These seem to go hand in hand, but a clear difference can be made between method and quality. We found instructor support to be more important when predicting students' well-being than general communication. Support is still a form of communication, but more direct and focused specific on the course content and learning outcomes. Thus, we argue that beyond the common ways in which teachers keep in contact with their students, they can play a bigger role in students' well-being by focusing more on direct, relevant feedback. This aspect is important since meetings can take place easier and more often online, due to their accessibility and convenience, but their number or type should not be used as an indicator of their effect on students. The COVID-19 pandemic offers a good justification to try out different ways of connecting students to their teachers, but the content and its quality should be emphasized and kept in mind when such interactions take place.

4.2 LIMITATIONS

The study took place over half an academic year during the pandemic. While it has a large scale, it still suffers from various shortcomings. A definite one is that teachers have different objectives and employ different structures from each other when organizing a course. This can affect the amount but especially the type of communication and support instructors offer. For example, less lectures could mean less communication and less support, but the same course could have different

methods to communicate and support students, such as higher number of short, small group meetings with the coordinator, more regular announcements and Q&As, and more literature with specific weekly goals provided. Such differences need to be accounted for when looking at instructor-level autonomy to better understand how it contributes to students' autonomy when studying. The way in which autonomy was measured in the current survey might also have implications for our results. Self-reported student autonomy seems a straightforward way to measure it, but its interpretation is highly dependent on students' view of their own learning behavior. This can be affected by previous learning experiences, learning strategies, time management, and individual goals. Similarly, while we know that the learning environment plays an important role in students' autonomy, it is not clear yet how to measure such an interaction and what is the exact role of the instructor in the environment. Teacher support and communication are a good measure for autonomy supportive variables, but they are not the only ones.

4.2 FUTURE DIRECTIONS

We emphasized the important role that teachers play in their students' well-being, but it is important to keep in mind that the most important factor is how students themselves perceive their autonomy when learning. This brings the problem at a more individual level. While there are certain methods already in practice on how to keep students' autonomy at a high level, mostly through the teacher^{[9][12]}, they are hard to adapt to each student. Future research should approach the problem and address autonomy directly, at an individual level. While instructors' communication did not significantly predict any of the well-being variables when controlling for student-level autonomy and instructor support, it did positively correlate with well-being and the other forms of autonomy. Communication could be mediated by other forms of autonomy, acting as a platform on how support is provided or even enhancing it. A similar argument can be formulated around instructor-level autonomy all together. Instructor-level autonomy could be a mediator between student-level autonomy and well-being. Further research is needed to examine its exact role.

4.3 CONCLUSION

To conclude, students' autonomy plays an essential role when looking at their well-being and motivation. Instructors' support should especially be considered when trying to reach such objectives during times of social distancing and online learning. Although the instructor communication is important, it plays a lesser role than relevant, direct support regarding learning materials. Educational policies, especially those related to online learning, need to approach such aspects explicitly. Employed techniques need to help teachers understand the importance of autonomy and how their academic interactions can play major roles in well-being and motivation of students.

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